

Pest Control and Management

DISEASES

A comparative study of six isolates of *Cochliobolus miyabeanus* in rice from USA

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We studied the morphology of conidia of six isolates of *Cochliobolus miyabeanus*, the causal organism of rice brown spot (BS), cultured on rabbit food agar (RFA), and tested the isolates for pathogenicity on four cultivars to identify physiologic races of the fungus.

The cultivars were inoculated 45 d after sowing by spraying an aqueous spore suspension of each isolate, adjusted to 4×10^4 spores/ml, on the 2 uppermost

fully extended leaves from 3 tillers. The reaction of each inoculated leaf was determined 10 d after inoculation by measuring the lesion size and counting the number of lesions on 20 cm² of leaf surface. Average disease ratings, scored on a 0-9 scale, are in Table 1. The conidia produced by the fungus on RFA were measured. The dimensions and number of septa of 100 conidia on each isolate were determined (Table 2).

Reaction, as expressed by lesion size, lesion number, and disease rating indicated that probably no physiologic specialization exists among the isolates tested. Average conidia size ranged from 60×10 μ m to 150×24.5 μ m, and number of septa per conidia ranged from 5 to 12.

Although the isolates had significantly differed in morphology and pathogenicity, and cultivars showed different susceptibilities, the isolate-by-variety interaction was insufficient to designate distinct physiologic races of the pathogens. □

Table 1. Average disease rating for varieties inoculated with 6 isolates of *C. miyabeanus*. Zaria, Nigeria, 1985.

Isolate	Disease rating ^a on				\bar{X}^b
	Dular (A)	Nova 76 (B)	Saturn (C)	Taichung Native 1 (D)	
LR579	4.58	3.62	3.45	2.16	3.45 bc
LR979	5.83	3.66	3.29	2.25	3.76 cd
LR1379	3.45	2.45	2.16	1.41	2.37 a
LR1979	3.62	2.33	1.83	1.58	2.34 a
LR2072a	7.33	6.00	6.54	5.20	6.27 d
LR2779	5.62	2.58	2.04	1.75	3.00 b
Means ^b	5.07 c	3.44 b	3.22 b	2.38 a	

^aBased on 0-9 scale for disease rating. ^bOverall means for isolates and varieties followed by the same letter do not differ significantly at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test.

Table 2. Variation in length, width, and number of septa of conidia from 6 isolates of *C. miyabeanus* cultured on RFA.

Isolate	Mean ^a		Range
	Length		
LR579	88.15	c	60.00-110.00
LR979	89.51	c	60.00-125.00
LR1379	95.65	b	65.00-115.00
LR1979	88.80	c	60.00-120.00
LR2072a	105.75	a	70.00-150.00
LR2779	86.20	c	65.00-130.00
	Width		
LR579	16.15	c	11.50-19.50
LR979	16.05	c	10.00-22.00
LR1379	15.80	c	12.00-19.00
LR1979	15.80	c	10.00-20.00
LR2072a	17.79	a	13.00-24.50
LR2779	16.80	b	11.50-22.50
	Number of septa		
LR579	7.77	b	6.00-11.00
LR979	7.51	b	5.00-10.00
LR1379	7.49	b	6.00-11.00
LR1979	7.39	b	5.00-10.00
LR2072a	8.59	a	6.00-12.00
LR2779	7.77	b	5.00-12.00

^aMeans for length, width, and number of septa of conidia, respectively, followed by the same letter do not differ significantly at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test.

Differentiation between the bacteria causing bacterial blight (BB), bacterial leaf streak (BLS), and bacterial brown blotch on rice

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We studied the causal agents of 34 *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* strains (causing BB), 14 *X. campestris* pv. *oryzicola* strains (causing BLS), and 6 brown blotch strains of diverse geographic

origins. We examined biochemical and enzymatic reactions and resistance patterns against different chemicals and conducted growth tests on C and N sources.

The three pathogens are separate, phenotypically different biological entities (see table). Four tests allow the differentiation of *X. campestris* pv. *oryzae* from *X. campestris* pv. *oryzicola*: acetoin production (-, +), growth on L-alanine as sole C source (-, +), growth on 0.2% vitamin-free casamino acids (-, +), and resistance to 0.001% Cu(NO₃)₂ (+, -). *X. campestris* pv. *oryzicola* strains are nutritionally less exacting than those from pv. *oryzae*. Adding 1% D-glucose or 1% cellobiose to 0.3%

vitamin-free casamino acids enhanced growth of all strains. Neither pathovar utilized ammonium as a sole N source with D-glucose or cellobiose as a C source, even with an added mixture of growth factors. This explains why Kado and Heskett's selective medium D5 (containing 1% cellobiose + 0.3% K₂HPO₄ + 0.1% NaH₂PO₄ + 0.1% NH₄Cl + 0.03% MgSO₄ · 7H₂O + 1.5% agar) is unsuitable for isolating *X. campestris* pv. *oryzae* or pv. *oryzicola*. SX selective medium (1% soluble potato starch + 0.1% meat extract + 0.5% NH₄Cl + 0.2% K₂HPO₄ + 0.002% methylgreen + 0.001% methylviolet 2B + 0.025% cycloheximide + 1.5% agar) also

did not support pathovar growth up to 10 d incubation. *X. campestris* pv. *oryzicola* is generally less susceptible to antibiotics such as 0.001% amoxycillin, 0.001% ampicillin, or 0.005% neomycin than *X. campestris* pv. *oryzae*. None of the phenotypic features was correlated with the virulence of the strains. It was not possible to phenotypically differentiate the pathogenic races or groups of *X. campestris* pv. *oryzae*.

Brown blotch strains share many features with *X. campestris* pv. *oryzae* and pv. *oryzicola*. They are singly-occurring gram-negative rods; they metabolize glucose oxidatively; they are catalase positive, indole negative, urease negative, nitrate reductase negative; they produce acid from D-glucose, are strictly aerobic, and do not utilize L-asparagine as sole C and N source. However, there are some striking differences between BB and BLS pathogens (see table). Besides those features, the following tendencies for differentiation exist: brown blotch isolates

Differentiation between the bacteria causing BB, BLS, and brown blotch on rice, RUG-IRRI.

	BB (<i>X. campestris</i> pv. <i>oryzae</i>)	BLS (<i>X. campestris</i> pv. <i>oryzicola</i>)	Brown blotch
Acetoin production	-	+	-
Oxidase	-	-	-
H ₂ S from peptone	+	+	-
Hydrolysis of TWEEN 60 and 80	+	+	-
Growth on L-alanine as sole C source	-	+	+
Growth on glycerol or sodium propionate as sole C source	-	-	+
Growth on 0.2% vitamin-free casamino acids	-	+	+
Growth on Kado and Heskett's selective medium	-	-	+
Resistance towards			
0.001% Cu(NO ₃) ₂	+	-	+
0.001% 8-hydroxyquinoline	-	-	+
0.001% ZnO	-	-	+

are gelatinase negative against 49% positives for *X. campestris* pv. *oryzae* and 100% for *X. campestris* pv. *oryzicola*, do not hydrolyze arbutin (91% and 67% positives), and are erythromycin resistant (0% and 7%).

Furthermore, they grow luxuriantly on Döbereiner N-free medium. DNA:rRNA hybridizations and % G+C determination showed that brown blotch isolates definitely do not belong in *Xanthomonas*. □

Severe ufra outbreak in transplanted rice in Bangladesh

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The transplanted rice crop in the 5,000-ha Dhaka-Narayanganj-Demra (DND) irrigation project area, about 20 km southeast of Dhaka, was badly infested by the stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus*, which causes ufra disease. Transplanted rice is continuously cropped in the project area except in some high elevation fields where mustard is grown in dry season. Symptoms

were white-splash pattern chlorosis, brown spots on leaves and culms at the growing points, and delayed panicle emergence.

Sporadic ufra attacks were first reported in early 1979. Disease incidence has gradually increased, with occasional severe outbreaks (see table). In Sep 1984 almost all fields were affected, with 5-100% infestation. Severity ranged from mild chlorosis to panicle nonemergence. Some plots were destroyed and farmers cut the plants for hay.

Most farmers used no ufra control, although a few used furadan at one-third the recommended dose of 33 kg/ha or 1.0 kg ai/ha. Fields previously planted to

mustard were least affected. About 7.5% of production (7,000-8,000 t) may be lost. Preliminary results of experiments with potted plants indicate that recommended doses of furadan, disulfoton, or fenamiphos applied to soil or as a foliar spray may cure infested plants. □

Estimated ufra severity and yield loss over several years in the DND project area, Bangladesh.

Year	Crop ^a	Infested fields (%)	Severity as % infested plants	Yield loss (%)
1978	T. aman	20-30	10-40	10
1981	Born	10-15	10-20	5
	T. aman	10-15	10-20	5
1982	Boro	10-15	10-20	5
	T. aman	20-25	10-40	10
1983	Boro	20-25	10-20	5
	T. aman	40-50	30-100	50
1984	Born	40-50	30-40	40
	T. aman	90-100	60-100	60-75

^a T. aman = transplanted aman.

Bacterial leaf streak (BLS) incidence in Nellore, Andhra Pradesh

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In late kharif 1983-84, a serious BLS outbreak, caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzicola*, occurred at Nellore for the first time. We surveyed farmers fields from Sep to Dec 1983 to assess disease severity.

The first BLS symptoms were observed the first week of Oct on 50- to 80-d-old, NLR9672, although all varieties developed typical symptoms. Varieties grown on smaller areas include NLR9674, NLR27999, and BCP.1. All the varieties